

On the Stability and Electrokinetic Potential of Copper and Cadmium Ferricyanide Sols

Nirmalendu Maitra

Negatively charged copper and cadmium ferricyanide sols have been prepared in a fairly pure condition with a view to determine their true zeta potential, in the presence of equicoagulating concentrations of different electrolytes. In the zone of rapid coagulation, this has been found to be 16.4 m.v., for copper ferricyanide sol. For cadmium ferricyanide sol, this has been found to be 24.7 m.v. in the zone of slow coagulation.

Rutgers¹ has shown that the true zeta potential (ζ) of a uniform glass capillary wall of radius 'r', in contact with a very dilute electrolyte solution, or in water can be determined by an equation of the form.

$$\zeta = \frac{4\pi\eta}{D} \cdot S \cdot \frac{E_s}{P} \left(1 + \frac{2x}{rS}\right) = \zeta_a \left(1 + \frac{2x}{rS}\right) \quad \dots \quad (1)$$

where E_s = Streaming potential
 P = the pressure used for streaming the liquid through the capillary
 x = the specific surface conductance
 S = the specific conductance of the liquid in bulk
 η = the coefficient of viscosity of the liquid
 D = the dielectric constant
 ζ_a = the apparent zeta potential

Ghosh² has deduced the equation,

$$\zeta = \zeta_a \left(1 + \frac{2\alpha x}{Sr}\right) \quad \dots \quad (2)$$

for the true zeta potential of a porous diaphragm where ' α ' is a correction factor.

Recently Ghosh³ has proposed the following equation for the true zeta potential of particles of As_2S_3 sol in the form of a diaphragm:

$$\frac{\zeta}{\zeta_a} = 1 + \frac{3x}{aR} \cdot \frac{1}{S} \quad \dots \quad (3)$$

1. Rutgers, *Trans. Farad. Soc.*, 1940, 36, 69.
2. Ghosh, *This Journal*, 1954, 31, 274, 393.
3. Ghosh, *Trans. Farad. Soc.*, 1953, 49, 1977.

Where R = radius of the spherical particles forming the diaphragm
 a = the ratio of the volume V_1 of liquid to volume V_2 of solid in the diaphragm:

The equation (3) has been found to hold good for a number of colloids. It can be expressed in the form,

$$\frac{1}{\zeta_s} = \frac{1}{\zeta} + m \frac{1}{S} \quad \dots \quad (4)$$

$$\text{where } m = \frac{3x}{a\zeta r}$$

For electrophoresis, Ghosh has shown that,

$$\frac{1}{U_s} = \frac{1}{U} + m' \frac{1}{S} \quad \dots \quad (5)$$

where U_s = apparent mobility of the colloid particles

U = true mobility of the particles

$$\text{and } m' = \frac{x}{UR}$$

No systematic investigation has been undertaken in the past to investigate the electro-kinetic behavior of any ferricyanide sol, in the light of the above theory. Hence, it was felt desirable to undertake a comprehensive investigation of the electrokinetic behavior of copper and cadmium ferricyanide sols and the present paper reports the results of this programme.

FIG. 1

FIG. 2

EXPERIMENTAL

Preparation of Copper Ferricyanide Sol.—To a solution of A. R. quality CuCl_2 (M/10) is added $\text{K}_3\text{Fe}(\text{CN})_6$ solution (M/10), until precipitation is just complete. The resulting green precipitate is peptized with a suitable excess of $\text{K}_3\text{Fe}(\text{CN})_6$ solution and dialysed

ON THE STABILITY AND ELECTROKINETIC POTENTIAL OF COPPER AND CADMIUM

in cellophane bags against distilled water for one month and allowed to age in a 6-litre jena flask, for two weeks, before our experiments started. The sol is found to be negatively charged. Its pH is 4.46 and the specific conductance at 25° is 2.36×10^{-4} mho cm^{-1} .

FIG. 3.

Preparation of Cadmium Ferricyanide Sol.—To an M/20 solution of A.R. quality $\text{K}_3\text{Fe}(\text{CN})_6$ is added dropwise, with vigorous stirring an equivalent quantity of a dilute solution of A. R. quality CdCl_2 (M/20). The slurry is allowed to stand for an hour, so that the heavier particles settle down. The slurry from the top is then shaken with an excess of $\text{K}_3\text{Fe}(\text{CN})_6$ solution and then allowed to dialyse in cellophane bags against distilled water. During dialysis, peptization of the precipitate occurs. After dialysis for three weeks, the sol is stored in a jena bottle and allowed to age for one month before the experiments started. The sol is found to be negatively charged. Its pH is 6.30 and specific conductance at 25°C is 2.39×10^{-4} mho cm^{-1} .

Equicoagulating Concentration of the Electrolytes.—The concentrations of different electrolytes which are just sufficient to bring about the coagulation of a definite volume of copper or cadmium ferricyanide sol, in approximately the same time have been termed the equicoagulating concentration and have been determined in the following way.

Copper Ferricyanide Sol.—Four pairs of similar, clean and dry pyrex glass test tubes are taken in a stand and marked 1, 2, 3, and 4. Two mls or slightly less of an electrolyte are taken in a test tube and the volume made up to 2 ml exactly with conductivity water. The concentration of the electrolyte thus differs from tube to tube. In the other series of the four test tubes, 2 ml of sol are taken. The electrolyte is first added to the colloid and the mixture is then poured back into the original tube which contained the electrolyte. The tubes containing the mixture are then allowed to stand for 15 min. avoiding jerking. At the end of 15 min., the tubes are centrifuged four at a time exactly for 2 min. at a definite speed. The supernatant liquid from the top is taken in a clear dry test tube and examined for transparency. Concentration of an electrolyte which in addition to the colloid gives just clear supernatant liquid by the above treatment is taken as its equicoagulating concentration. The following electrolytes have been used, BaCl_2 , $\text{La}(\text{NO}_3)_3$, and mixtures of KCl and BaCl_2 , and KCl and $\text{La}(\text{NO}_3)_3$.

Cadmium Ferricyanide.—The method for this sol is exactly the same except the time of coagulation of the sol electrolyte mixture, which in this case is 24 hr. The electrolytes used are KCl , BaCl_2 , $\text{La}(\text{NO}_3)_3$, and mixtures of KCl with BaCl_2 and $\text{La}(\text{NO}_3)_3$.

Electroosmotic Experiments with Copper Ferricyanide Coagula at 25°.—A definite volume (30 ml.) of the copper ferricyanide sol is pipetted into a clean dry bottle and to it, is added an equal volume of electrolyte of the desired concentration. After allowing the mixture to stand for 15 min., the coagula are separated from the supernatant solution by centrifuging the mixture at a suitable speed (2500 rpm). The entire coagula are then transferred into the U-tube with a little supernatant solution, and a diaphragm is made therein by centrifuging the system at a suitable speed (2500 rpm) for 15-20 min. For a particular set of experiments, the volume of the diaphragm within the U-tube is maintained the same by adjusting its time of rotation. This ensures the constancy in the value of m , assuming that X remained constant, at the equicoagulating point. The U-tube containing the diaphragm is filled with the supernatant liquid and the electroosmotic velocity is measured by the moving air bubble method of Mukherjee *et al.*⁴ The electroosmotic data for rapid coagulation of copper ferricyanide sol are recorded in Table I.

TABLE I

Electroosmotic Data for Copper Ferricyanide Sols at 25°
Rapid Rate of Coagulation—15 minutes

Electrolyte	Equicoagulative conc ^m in (N)	Specific Conductance of Supernatant $S \times 10^3$	$\frac{I}{S} \times 10^{-3}$	ζ_0 in m.v.	$\frac{1}{\zeta_0} \times 10^{-4}$
KCl & BaCl ₂ }	4.99×10^{-3}	1.361	7.348	15.70	6.369
	4.69×10^{-3}				
BaCl ₂	4.29×10^{-3}	0.6782	14.75	15.2	6.579
La (NO ₃) ₃	8.72×10^{-4}	0.2241	44.62	14.3	6.993
KCl & La (NO ₃) ₃ }	4.99×10^{-4}	0.2682	37.28	15.1	6.628
	7.75×10^{-4}				
KCl & La (NO ₃) ₃ }	1.49×10^{-3}	3.3933	25.43	15.7	6.368
	7.46×10^{-4}				

Microcataphoretic Experiments with Copper and Cadmium Ferricyanide Particles at 25°.—The mobility of the colloidal particles is determined by means of a microcataphoretic apparatus, described by Chakraborty and Ghosh⁵. The microscope with which the particles of copper ferricyanide and cadmium ferricyanide are observed in the cell carried a micrometer scale in the eyepiece. With the help of the scale, the particles of the desired size can be selected very easily. The average time taken to cover a given distance for direct and reverse motion is used for calculation. The results for copper and cadmium ferricyanide sols are recorded in Tables II and III.

4. Mukherjee *et al.*, *This Journal*, 1927, 4, 493.

5. Chakraborty and Ghosh, *This Journal*, 1933, 40, 423.

TABLE II

Microcataphoretic Data on the Particles of Copper Ferricyanide Sol at 25°

Rapid Rate of Coagulation

Radius of the Particles = 2.0 μ Area of Cross Section of the Cell
= 0.2517 Sq. cm.

Electrolyte	Equicoagulative conc ^m in (N)	Specific Conductance $S \times 10^3$	$\frac{1}{S} \times 10^{-3}$	Mobility U_a in cm/sec/volt/cm	$\frac{1}{U_a} \times 10^{-4}$
KCl & BaCl ₂ }	4.99 $\times 10^{-3}$	1.351	7.348	1.27	0.7843
	4.69 $\times 10^{-3}$				
BaCl ₂ & La(NO ₃) ₃ }	4.29 $\times 10^{-3}$	0.6782	14.75	1.28	0.7813
	8.72 $\times 10^{-4}$	0.2241	44.62	1.26	0.7937
KCl & La(NO ₃) ₃ }	4.99 $\times 10^{-4}$	0.2682	37.28	1.25	0.8000
	7.75 $\times 10^{-4}$				
KCl & La(NO ₃) ₃ }	1.49 $\times 10^{-3}$	0.3933	25.43	1.28	0.7813
	7.46 $\times 10^{-4}$				

TABLE III

Microcataphoretic Data on the Particles of Cadmium Ferricyanide Sol at 25°

Slow Rate of Coagulation (24 hours)

Diameter of the particles = 4.0 μ Area of Cross Section of the Cell
= 0.2517 Sq. cm

Electrolyte	Equicoagulative conc ^m in (N)	Specific Conductance $S \times 10^3$	$\frac{1}{S} \times 10^{-3}$	Mobility $U_a \times 10^4$	$\frac{1}{U_a} \times 10^{-4}$
KCl	1.50 $\times 10^{-3}$	2.208	4.529	1.82	0.5495
BaCl ₂	1.04 $\times 10^{-3}$	0.287	34.84	1.35	0.7407
La(NO ₃) ₃	3.90 $\times 10^{-4}$	0.1640	60.98	1.11	0.9009
KCl & BaCl ₂ }	5.00 $\times 10^{-3}$	0.9729	10.28	1.69	0.5917
	9.60 $\times 10^{-4}$				
KCl & La(NO ₃) ₃ }	2.50 $\times 10^{-3}$	0.6001	16.67	1.58	0.6329
	2.70 $\times 10^{-4}$				
KCl & La(NO ₃) ₃ }	5.00 $\times 10^{-4}$	0.2392	41.80	1.29	0.7752
	3.30 $\times 10^{-4}$				

DISCUSSION

An examination of the data recorded in Tables I, II, and III reveals that the specific conductivities of the supernatant liquids as expected decrease with decreasing concentrations of the equicoagulating electrolytes containing counter ions of different valency. The observed values of ζ_a or the observed mobility U_a , decrease when the valency of the counter ions increase. The ion relaxation effect is quite negligible in our experiments which are restricted to large particles and fairly high concentration of electrolytes. The electro-

viscous effect is also negligible in the present case, if the value of 'f', the electroviscous constant is small, i.e., $\frac{10.2 \times 10^{-11}}{80} \text{ V}^{-1} \text{ cm}^2$, as pointed out by Hunter and Alexander⁶.

Hence the variation in the value of ζ_a or U_a is attributed to the surface conductance effect only. This view is justified from the plots of $1/\zeta_a$ against $1/S$ or $1/U_a$ against $1/S$ which are fairly good straight lines (Figs. 1, 2, and 3), in accordance with the equations (4) and (5). The value of true zeta potential of copper ferricyanide sol is therefore obtained from the intercept on the $1/\zeta_a$ axis in the case of electroosmotic experiments. The true zeta potential is calculated from the true electrophoretic mobility obtained from the intercept on the $1/U_a$ axis using Smoluchowski's equation for electrophoresis. In this manner the true zeta potential of copper ferricyanide sol is found to be 16.1 m.v. from electroosmotic experiments and 16.6 m.v. from microcataphoretic experiments. The agreement between the two values is quite satisfactory and hence their mean value, i.e., 16.4 m.v. is taken to be the true zeta potential of copper ferricyanide sol, in the presence of equicoagulating concentrations of electrolytes, where the time of coagulation is 15 minutes. Similarly the value of true zeta potential is found to be 24.7 m.v. for cadmium ferricyanide sol in the zone of slow coagulation (time of coagulation — 24 hours).

The author expresses his grateful thanks to Professor B. N. Ghosh, D.S.C., F.N.I., Department of Chemistry, University of Calcutta, for the laboratory facilities.

DEPARTMENT OF CHEMISTRY,
UNIVERSITY OF CALCUTTA,
CALCUTTA—9.

Received August 2, 1966.